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Exploring Consumption's Neglected Socio-cultural Dimension within Macromarketing Thought

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Abstract. Technological efficiency alone cannot ensure sustainable patterns of ICT use. To understand how digitalization intersects with Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), it is necessary to move beyond purely technical solutions and incorporate socio-cultural perspectives. Current approaches in ICT for Sustainability (ICT4S) often operate under developmental assumptions in macromarketing, yet a critical perspective highlights the importance of consumer culture and sufficiency strategies. This shift parallels educational practices, where learners must acquire not only technical skills but also the capacity to act as informed agents in digital and sustainable transformations. By recognizing the macro-level social practices that shape ICT consumption, educational frameworks can integrate sufficiency-oriented strategies into curricula, preparing individuals to make responsible decisions. Policy and governance provide the structural conditions for this transformation, but it is through education that factual knowledge, critical reflection, and active participation are cultivated. Embedding socio-cultural dimensions into ICT design and marketing thus complements educational goals, fostering value creation while equipping learners, teachers, and institutions to engage proactively with sustainability and digitalization.

Keywords: Sufficiency, Macromarketing, Consumer Culture Theory, Environmental informatics, Sustainable human-computer interaction, Resource decoupling.

1 Introduction

This discussion focuses on the question of *how to adapt to society's new expectations*. In this paper, new expectations are defined as consumer beliefs and values that are oriented towards sustainability.

Conventionally, the relationship between the marketing system and societal consumption assumes that the more the individual consumes, the happier this individual becomes. Scholars who looked more closely into this relationship found that beyond a certain point, there is a negative relationship between consumption levels and subjective well-being (Deckop et al., 2010; Pieters, 2013; Podoshen & Andrzejewski, 2012). There are limits to the satisfaction that relentless consumption brings to society, accordingly organizing value-creation for information and communication technologies (ICT) requires considering how to integrate a notion of *enough* or sufficient consumption, this objective is pursued through drawing attention to the marketing systems perspectives. This conceptual contribution discusses some of the controversies involved in such an endeavor and proposes Consumer Culture Theory research to address the sparse work in macromarketing.

Based on findings from the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2008), there is general agreement that consumer habits and the ways in which goods and services are provided need to change since the existing global consumption patterns are not sustainable. Researchers and industry increasingly extend this statement to the way ICTs are produced and consumed (Rouăinia, 2014). Whether a reduction of consumption levels should be encouraged remains a hotly discussed issue. At this point, many experts would agree that an alteration or transformation of consumption is required. Often, concrete measures are left to the discretion of the individual stakeholders, with little efforts for coordination. This indeterminacy may distract actors from working towards results at different levels.

Currently, there is no global governance regulatory strategy to limit the resource consumption of ICTs (Mont & Plepys, 2008). Well-known strategies to reach sustainability objectives, such as *sufficiency* (for an overview, see Sandberg 2021), need to be adjusted to the issue area of ICTs. At present, what is known about sufficiency is not properly grounded in the social practices of ICT users. Consumption derives from practices (Christensen & Røpke, 2010); therefore, future devices have to integrate the requirements of sustainability-oriented users. Consumer Culture Theory has most consistently been associated with interpretive strategies of consumers during consumption.

This contribution advocates that the concept of sufficiency should be explored as a crucial aspect of consumer behavior. Sustainability-oriented consumers' lived experiences offer insights for future ICT value-creation (Liedtke et al., 2015).

Based on these challenges, this paper seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How is the norm of sustainability operationalized within marketing systems?
2. How can interpretative strategies for sufficient consumption of smartphones be included in the development of sustainable ICT?

Sufficiency is understood as a contextual knowledge of resource limitation (Gorge et al., 2015), which may be found within the core values and practices of consumption communities (Svenson, 2018, 2019; Svenson et al. 2018). To contribute to sustainable consumption, a conception of sufficiency is needed, few consumers consciously have a conception of sufficiency. It is a cultural trait that is context-specific and has to be unearthed through qualitative market research. This concept, as understood here, examines individual users not in isolation but as members of a group, often mediated through an online activity. Being immersed within a collective can help consumers to uphold sufficiency as a value. Consumption is understood as being socially and culturally embedded, while being closely linked to technical systems (Schmutzer, 1994). Upon realizing the systemic character of consumption patterns, the starting points for a change in these consumption patterns become palpable (Brand, 2008).

Sustainability is still a nascent research area in ICT. Insights developed outside of information systems (IS) research may provide further alignment between IS applications at the micro level of social practices and the often-overlooked macro-societal background.

IS are known to be a key to managing sustainability issues in organizations and households. New technology options are a sound way to improve energy efficiency. Raising awareness for sustainability issues is appropriate, but an understanding of what choices consumers are willing to pursue leads us towards an exploration of consumer practices in the sphere of ICT. Organizing value creation for ICT requires an integration of user groups into the development of more sustainable ICTs and a keen attention to societal challenges.

To approach the described challenges, it is necessary to cross disciplinary borders and integrate ICT engineering with the social sciences (Mickoleit, 2010). The concept of human interests (Habermas, 1987) recognizes the strength of different academic traditions. This concept adheres to the following three-fold purpose (Willmott, 1997):

- enhancement of a mutual understanding (historical-hermeneutic science),
- improvement of prediction and control (empirical-analytic science), and the
- realization of more rational social relations (critical science).

First, we want to understand ICT consumption, thereby improving mutual understanding among consumers, businesses, and society. Here, recourse to ethnographic research is taken to understand the lived experiences inside consumer culture (e.g., McCracken, 1990, 2005).

Second, we strive to enhance prediction and control concerning the interactive functions of software and hardware, as well as the meaning-making of consumers. Eventually, this would result in guide boards, which could help designers alter their

products to make them more sustainable to fit the demands of the changing ICT consumption market.

Third, through an understanding of the lived experiences of consumers, predictors of sustainability-oriented practices shall be generated, which may be integrated into the design of soft- and hardware, supporting the development of more rational social relations. In addition to this *built-in* sustainability, marketing these ICT devices could be combined with user guides detailing the advantages of sustainability-oriented action (Heidmann et al., 2011; Mickoleit, 2010). Thus, an interdisciplinary approach to seeking knowledge of consumers may help reduce the negative impact of ICT consumption and strive to realize the enlightenment project.

In practical terms, the Consumer Culture Theory approach calls for empirical research that observes and listens to consumers, initiates a dialogue between consumers and businesses, and works towards a transformation of ICT consumption (Stiel & Teuteberg, 2015).

The combination of Consumer Culture Theory and Macromarketing promises to highlight how consumer practices are impacted by macro social forces, but also how consumers endeavor to resist dominant attitudes in the market. Macromarketing typically tackles the macro-societal background of the marketing phenomena between business and consumers. Macromarketing investigates how the marketing system affects society and then further formulates recommendations for micro-level actors. By analogy, macromarketing thought bears the potential to bridge the micro-macro divide, which is also found in IS research. Because macromarketing investigates the challenges at the conjunction between marketing and society, it may provide a background perspective for the sustainability challenges encountered in IS research.

2 **Production, Consumption, and the Marketing System**

Sales of ICT devices have increased tremendously over the past decade. Depending on the disciplinary affiliation, consumption patterns of smartphone usage could also be circumscribed as a pattern of overconsumption or hyperconsumption (Albinsson et al., 2010). The world's natural resources are scarce, and overall consumption in the global north remains at high levels. Considering the population growth and the increasing spread of ICTs in the global south (Cohen, 1995; Tukker et al., 2010), it becomes obvious that our planet may not easily bear the consumption rates of recent decades in a consumerist society. These challenges, which involve fairness and distributive justice issues, have led to a surge of interest in more sustainable societal arrangements (Shapiro, 2009). Ecological issues and the relation to the marketing system are by now the focal activity of well-established expert communities, e.g., the techniques of cleaner production. A renegade position is the one that critically scrutinizes consumption.

In colloquial language, people sometimes reduce marketing to a narrow business activity (Kotler & Levy, 1969). Per a contemporary definition, “Marketing is the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large” (AMA, 2013). This study supports the normative objective of sustainability, focusing on the social, ecological, and economic effects of present-day consumption. The question remains: how is the norm of sustainability operationalized within marketing systems? In this regard, macromarketing provides relevant standpoints (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014) and mirrors some of the guiding principles of IS research for sustainability.

2.1 Macromarketing and Sustainability

Macromarketing offers a comprehensive perspective on the collective behaviour of microeconomic actors. The macromarketing view places demands for the investigation of the impact and consequences that marketing – as a practice – has on society and vice versa (Hunt, 2012). The Dominant Social Paradigm (Kilbourne et al., 1997) is a concept in macromarketing that circumscribes how Western industrial culture and the consumption ethos intermingle. It has also been defined as “the collection of norms, beliefs, values, habits, and so on that form the world view most commonly held within a culture” (Pirages & Ehrlich, 1974). Mittelstaedt and colleagues (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014) identify the following five dimensions that repeatedly feature in discussions of the Dominant Social Paradigm: the technological, political, economic, anthropocentric, and competitive. Different values will be present for any of these dimensions given the overall socio-economic situation in which a society finds itself or the level of development it has reached. The degree of value variation present within a society is considered a signifier of its Dominant Social Paradigm. To implement this concept for a range of actors (including different academic disciplines) who wish to coalesce around sustainable consumption, approaches for transdisciplinary sustainability research have been developed (Schäfer et al., 2010).

This research stream introduces the main tenets of a macromarketing conception of sustainability applicable to ICTs (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014). The two perspectives are introduced for analytical purposes and do not fundamentally contradict each other. The following two dimensions are chosen: the claim about the nature of society and the role of technology. The two perspectives are introduced for analytical purposes and do not principally contradict each other. The following two dimensions are chosen: the claim about the nature of society and the role of technology. Either adopted perspective provides a different framing for the future value creation of IS and ICTs (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014).

2.1.1 The Developmental School

The developmental school of macromarketing subscribes to a sociology of order (Dahrendorf, 1959), which means that for the marketing system to meet societal needs, some additional sustainability indicators have to be added to the consumer and corporate agendas. An example of action stemming from this approach would be to vow for a compulsory sustainability index of corporations. Consumers would then have additional criteria from which to choose for a range of market offerings.

The developmental school of sustainability considers it enough to include sustainability ideals into the materialism that characterizes the Dominant Social Paradigm. Including a sustainable marketing orientation in managerial strategy (Mitchell et al., 2010) is another example of concrete measures taken by this school.

The developmental position considers the eco-innovations of corporations and consumers willing to vote with their pocketbooks as the viable path towards greater sustainability. Sustainability is cast as a technical problem for corporations, such as considering how technological progress is possible without increased carbon emissions (Hall et al., 2010; Moore & Manring, 2009).

2.1.2 The Critical School

The critical school of sustainability subscribes to a sociology of conflict (Dahrendorf, 1959), which means that the “gains of marketing to human welfare come at the expense of others (in other societies, or in future generations) or the environment” (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014). Conflict stems from the disequilibrium of resources, and the effects of markets are not considered sustainable. Instead, other organizing principles are sought (Cheney et al., 2014) that promise a renunciation of the Dominant Social Paradigm’s basic principle (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014). The materialism inherent in the Dominant Social Paradigm is questioned, characterizing it through a materialism of “more is good” (Peterson, 2013, p. 312) and a purely pragmatic criterion of market success, i.e., “if it works, it must be good” (Peterson, 2013, p. 312).

The critical position holds that the economic system produces values, which, understood as materialism and consumerism, are the central environmental problem. These may be cured only through values, such as frugality, community-orientation and sufficiency (Geels et al., 2015). The critical school of macromarketing holds that the latter value should matter the most regarding strategies for reaching sustainability. Regarding the role of technology, the critical school diagnoses a market failure for curing the problem of sustainability. Societal challenges may require more nuanced solutions than technology alone. Given the reliance of the Dominant Social Paradigm on technology, it becomes difficult to distance oneself from the position that technology may cure everything (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014).

2.2 Efficiency in the Production of ICT

Decoupling economic development from its impact on the environment is important to foster sustainability. A United Nations report (Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011) proposes resource decoupling, which is defined as lowering the rate of use of primary resources per unit of economic activity, as a way towards sustainability. In principle, ICT can foster this very objective. “The long-term availability of ICT services may enable and foster a transition to a less material-intensive economy” (Hilty, 2008, p. 154). For some time, efficiency-enhancing strategies have been pursued in production to help ICT take on this role.

Increasing degrees of technological efficiency may lead to a rebound effect in which the gains of efficiency result in additional consumption. This is the core of Jevons’ paradox (Alcott et al., 2012). The core problem is that “resource decoupling may result in a growth rate higher than the decoupling rate, therefore counteracting the resource-saving effects of decoupling” (Hilty et al., 2011).

Jevons’ paradox can be observed in the field of ICT. For example, computations per kilowatt-hour over time have become more *efficient*: “energy efficiency in computing, expressed in computations per energy input, has doubled every 1.57 years between 1947 and 2009” (Kooimey et al., 2011a, 2011b). This increased efficiency illustrates how technological advances lead to resource savings, which are then used as an opportunity to increase performance. The problem is that compared with the past, a greater number of people have ICTs today, and these people possess more ICT devices. The conclusion that may be drawn here is that there is a strong increase in the demand of electricity for computing, despite the best efforts by technology experts to increase efficiency (Hilty et al., 2011). When an efficiency approach to environmental sustainability is taken, the underlying assumption is often that societal systems require incremental changes in the organization of production and everyday practices (Geels et al., 2015). The potential contribution of existing approaches to using ICT in the service of sustainability, including Environmental Informatics, Green IT, and Sustainable Human-Computer Interaction, is diminished because rebound effects are ignored (Hilty et al., 2011).

Notwithstanding their valuable contributions to sustainable ICT, all of these approaches have been criticized, since they restrict themselves to increasing efficiency leaving the context of resource limitation unattended (Hilty et al., 2011). Such resource limitation, understood as sufficiency, has only recently been regarded as a viable way to promote sustainable ICT innovations (Pettersen, 2016).

Political regulation has been proposed as a measure to implement a shortage of resources and to diminish the rebound effects that curb the positive impact of following the efficiency principle in ICT for sustainability (ICT4S) (Hilty et al., 2011). A cultural

context of resource limitation appears to be a sensible objective but is lacking substance.

The discussion by Hilty et al. (2011) reveals that ICT4S has been operating with a trajectory that strongly resembles that of the developmental school of macromarketing. The shortcomings of such a perspective are that sufficiency strategies are the blind spot of this perspective. This perspective does not seem to consider Jevons' (1906) earlier insight that the critical issue is not the final exhaustion of resources but the point at which production peaks and begins to decline..

The developmental school considers sustainability to be a simple add-on to the present state of society. In other words, the Dominant Social Paradigm needs to be extended to accommodate sustainability traits. The theoretical advantages of more efficiency are often not capitalized in practice. For example, the influence of user behavior in household energy consumption outweighs efficiency-enhancing technical artifacts (Liedtke et al., 2015; Sunikka-Blank & Galvin, 2012).

Efficiency measures alone will not bring about sustainability. Measures in the sphere of consistency and sufficiency are needed to support efficiency measures. Achieving this knowledge of everyday consumption patterns (Christensen & Røpke, 2010) requires interlocking with the culturally distinct meanings (McCracken, 1990, 2005) consumer groups attach to ICT artifacts. Consumer Culture Theory (for an overview, see Hungara & Nobre, 2021) appears as a suitable academic field to supplement the marketing systems perspective. Sustainable consumption may become a reality only when the meaning consumers attach to material things does not contradict the objective of sustainability. Consumer Culture Theory is used to decipher the *right* meanings for sustainability-oriented consumption, such as sufficiency.

2.3 Sufficiency in the Consumption of ICTs

The developmental school of macromarketing values the efforts of the different actors, who work towards efficiency-enhancing technology solutions. Seen through the lens of the critical school, Jevons' paradox is a splendid illustration of the marketing system's failure to cater to the societal challenge of sustainability. In the developmental school of macromarketing, no effective ceiling of resource consumption is intended. It is exactly at this point that the critical school may offer an alternative way to address resource depletion. The innovativeness of the private sector may support sufficiency strategies, following the example of sufficiency-based business models (Bocken & Short, 2015).

Discussions on technological innovation and socio-economic development have shown that technology alone does not cure societal challenges (Heeks, 2010). Instead, socio-cultural insights should be added to value-creation activities of marketers (Svenson, 2018). Rather it can be very useful to work with marketing to educate the market ahead of itself (Oakey, 2003). ICT's potential to fulfill the objective of

sustainability may be utilized only if the social dimension of consumption is considered (Grunfeld, 2013). It is impossible to bring about a lasting reduction of resource consumption based solely on production-side efficiency, as witnessed in Jevons' paradox.

In addition to curbing resource consumption on the macro-level through political regulation, some measures that are accessible to private sector actors may bring the socio-cultural dimension into ICT4S. Both the developmental and critical schools consider purchasing to be of prime importance vis-à-vis the Dominant Social Paradigm (Mittelstaedt et al., 2014). In addition, the critical school seeks to uncover the values that guide purchasing and anti-consumption, when political or ethical statements are attached. Consumption communities form around everyday practices consumers value highly (Svenson 2018; Svenson et al., 2018; Svenson 2019). Here, consumers increasingly demand transparency from corporations (Papaoikonomou & Alarcón, 2015). These demands find expression in acts of both consumption and non-consumption (Cherrier, 2009). Corporations are likely to appropriate sustainability issues because they would not want to display indifference to macromarketing challenges (Kotler, 2011). As communities seek to impact corporate sustainability policy (McDonagh et al., 2012), an increase in corporate accountability follows (Meyer & Kirby, 2010).

Those consumers referred to as either downshiffters or voluntary simplifiers or those who choose to live off-grid are examples of consumer groups that match these criteria (Håkansson & Sengers, 2013). The sustainable lifestyle of these consumers is praised, but their small numbers mean that their overall sustainable impact is rather small (McDonagh et al., 2012). Because it is necessary to question the ideology of consumption, examples of consumers who try to think differently are an important source of insight. The beliefs and values of these groups provide starting points that may help increase the innovative potential that rests with the value-creation of ICT designers.

Thus far, studies that reveal how sufficiency can be introduced into the production-dominated sphere of ICT research are lacking. User-integration into ICT design is appreciated, but the integration of users with expert knowledge on sufficiency is deemed necessary. Users that are oriented towards sufficiency have been shown to display norms of their own (e.g., Svenson, 2019). Resource limitation is more tangible for these users. Instead of randomly choosing test users, attention to naturally existing communities promises better insights into sustainable consumption, e.g., in the Fairphone brand community (e.g., Svenson 2018; Svenson et al., 2018; Svenson 2019)).

The logic of sufficiency holds that there is a quantity of marketable products that is just sufficient for personal happiness, thereby avoiding under-consumption as well as overconsumption (Princen, 2005). The optimal level of consumption remains an unsolved but enticing question.

2.4 The Reconfigurative Position

The two schools of macromarketing may spur each other in the pursuit of sustainability given that they are joined in dialogue. However, a further *reconfigurative* position (Geels et al., 2015) seeks to bridge the analytical gap between the marketing system and the attitudes, meanings and motivations of consumer groups. This reconfigurative vision (Geels et al., 2015) may align the developmental and critical schools of macromarketing. The unit of analysis proposed by the reconfigurative position is the transformation of socio-technical systems and daily life practices in particular domains, such as mobility or energy use. In contrast to the two macromarketing schools, the reconfigurative position “shifts the analytical focus from the purchasing of products and services [...] towards the accomplishment of daily practices” (Geels et al., 2015, p. 6). Today, many everyday practices integrate ICTs in one way or another (Christensen & Røpke, 2010), which is why this perspective deserves further elaboration in ICT4S.

Research on ICT production and research on ICT consumption appear separated, which might be consistent with scientific rigor but does little to address the concurrence of the spheres of production and consumption. The interrelation of production and consumption may be operationalized through a combination of different cognitive interests (Habermas, 1987). The practical human interest that attends to understanding sufficiency-oriented consumers should be used to deduct requirements that are then processed by the technical cognitive (human) interest. This technical interest attends to the efficiency criterion. In addition, the critical cognitive interest should then drive sustainability-oriented innovations to tackle the societal challenges encountered in the organization of ICTs. When all three cognitive interests are applied and balanced, greater sustainability gains may be brought about.

The meanings consumers attach to ICT devices and the daily practices that integrate ICTs may provide the raw materials required for engineers to foster sufficiency solutions to the sustainability challenge. If these cultural traits can be integrated into the usage of ICTs in networks, then the aforementioned societal challenges may be tackled. Such a solution requires the development of ICTs together with users from sustainability-oriented subcultures (e.g., Svenson, 2018; Svenson et al., 2018; Svenson, 2019)

3 Outlook on Efficiency and Sufficiency in ICT

By embracing the critical school of macromarketing, future pathways to alleviate the challenges that stem from the consumption of ICTs have been explored. Marketing can adapt to the new expectations of society by considering unheard voices from downshifters or voluntary simplifiers.

The findings of the critical school of macromarketing note that consumer groups have the potential to approach sufficiency as a form of adaptation or resilience vis-à-

vis resource limitation. Taking the example of battery practices, iPhone users practiced sufficiency as a perceived obligation (Svenson et al., 2018), because of the product's closed design rather than as a voluntary choice. Consumers require a collective to uphold sufficiency as a value and Consumer Culture Theory research may tap into the interpretative strategies of users. IS are ubiquitous and bear the potential to support the value of sufficiency. In this way, more sustainable consumption of ICT could take shape.

There is some research that excavates a conceptualization of sufficient consumption from naturally existing consumption communities (Svenson, 2018) laying the foundation for the development of ICT for sustainability, going beyond the confinement of efficiency. By means of open innovation or living labs, the subjective knowledge of users, who are aware of resource limitations, may be generated for integration.

The guiding principles that inform sustainable ICT were traditionally restricted to efficiency strategies (Alcott et al., 2012). Earlier studies considered only political regulation as the source providing the context of resource limitation (Jänicke, 2008). IS research can address changing market demands by communicating with sustainability-conscious customer groups. The political agenda should include ICT sufficiency strategies. Social impact of IS research may benefit from sustainability-oriented consumer groups' insights.

Netnographic studies of online user groups who practice sufficient consumption (Svenson, 2018) highlighting the development of an information system that facilitates the collaboration of a range of different actors involved in the process of developing more sustainable ICT (Asswad et al., 2018) is feasible. Future research can support the movement of ICT4S by addressing the following items:

- A conceptualization for sufficient consumption (Sandberg, 2021)
- The interaction of user groups who practice sufficient consumption with producers and political actors (Saatcioglu & Corus, 2019)
- Methods for integrating sufficient consumers into the development of sustainable ICT (Asswad et al., 2018)

This contribution has integrated the perspectives of macromarketing, focusing on marketing and society as well as ICT designers. Through using Habermas' social theoretical concepts of cognitive interests, it could be shown that ICT designers have limited their attention too much on technical peculiarities, while neglecting the socio-cultural dimension, represented by research in the tradition of Consumer Culture Theory.

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References

- Albinsson, P. A., Wolf, M., & Kopf, D. A. (2010). Anti-consumption in East Germany: consumer resistance to hyperconsumption. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 9(6), 412-425.
- Alcott, B., Giampietro, M., Mayumi, K., & Polimeni, J. (2012). *The Jevons Paradox and the Myth of Resource Efficiency Improvements*. Earthscan.
- Asswad, J., Hake, G., Gómez, J. M. (2018). The service point of the future for sustainable smartphone development. In: Nachhaltige Betriebliche Umweltinformationssysteme, pp. 53-62. Springer Gabler, Wiesbaden.
- AMA. (2013). Definition of Marketing. <https://www.ama.org/AboutAMA/Pages/Definition-of-Marketing.aspx>
- Bocken, N. M. P., & Short, S. W. (2015). Towards a sufficiency-driven business model: Experiences and opportunities. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*.
- Brand, K. W. (2008). Konsum im Kontext. Der „verantwortliche Konsument“ – ein Motor nachhaltigen Konsums? In: H. Lange (Ed.), *Nachhaltigkeit als radikaler Wandel* (pp. 71-93). VS.
- Cheney, G., Santa Cruz, I., Peredo, A. M., & Nazareno, E. (2014). Worker cooperatives as an organizational alternative: Challenges, achievements and promise in business governance and ownership. *Organization*, 21(5), 591-603.
- Cherrier, H. (2009). Anti-consumption discourses and consumer-resistant identities. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(2), 181-190.
- Christensen, T. H., & Røpke, I. (2010). Can practice theory inspire studies of ICTs in everyday life? In B. Bräuchler & J. Postill (Eds.), *Theorising media and practice* (pp. 233-256). Berghahn.
- Cohen, J. E. (1995). How many people can the earth support? *The Sciences*, 35(6), 18-23.
- Dahrendorf, R. (1959). *Class and class conflict in industrial society*. Stanford University Press.
- Deckop, J. R., Jurkiewicz, C. L., & Giacalone, R. A. (2010). Effects of materialism on work-related personal well-being. *Human Relations*, 63(7), 1007-1030.
- Fischer-Kowalski, M., Swilling, M., von Weizsäcker, E. U., Ren, Y., Moriguchi, Y., Crane, W., Krausmann, F., Eisenmenger, N., Giljum, S., Hennicke, P., Romero Lankao, P., & Siriban Manalang, A. (2011). *Decoupling: natural resource use and environmental impacts from economic growth*.
- Geels, F. W., McMeekin, A., Mylan, J., & Southerton, D. (2015). A critical appraisal of Sustainable Consumption and Production research: The reformist, revolutionary and reconfiguration positions. *Global Environmental Change*, 34, 1-12.

- Gorge, H., Herbert, M., Özcaglar-Toulouse, N., & Robert, I. (2015). What Do We Really Need? Questioning Consumption Through Sufficiency. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 35(1), 11-22.
- Grunfeld, H. (2013). ICT for sustainable development: an example from Cambodia. *The Journal of Community Informatics*, 10(2).
- Habermas, J. (1987). *Knowledge and human interests*. Polity.
- Hall, J. K., Daneke, G. A., & Lenox, M. J. (2010). Sustainable development and entrepreneurship: Past contributions and future directions. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 25(5), 439-448.
- Heeks, R. (2010). Do information and communication technologies (ICTs) contribute to development? *Journal of International Development*, 22(5), 625-640.
- Heidmann, F., Bauer, J., & Warth, A. (2011). Eine Smartphone-App für einen nachhaltigen Lebensstil. *Ökologisches Wirtschaften*(4), 21-22.
- Hilty, L. (2008). *Information technology and sustainability: Essays on the relationships between information technology and sustainable development*. Books on Demand.
- Hilty, L., Lohmann, W., & Huang, E. (2011). Sustainability and ICT - an overview of the field. *Politeia*, 27(104), 13-28.
- Hungara, A., & Nobre, H. (2021). A consumer culture theory perspective of the marketplace: An integrative review and agenda for research. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 45(4), 805-823.
- Hunt, S. D. (2012). Toward the Institutionalization of Macromarketing: Sustainable Enterprise, Sustainable Marketing, Sustainable Development, and the Sustainable Society. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 32(4), 404-411.
- Håkansson, M., & Sengers, P. (2013). Beyond being green: simple living families and ICT. Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems.
- Jänicke, M. (2008). *Ecological modernisation: New perspectives*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16(5), 557-565.
- Jevons, W. S. (1906). *The coal question: an inquiry concerning the progress of the nation, and the probable exhaustion of our coal-mines*. Macmillan.
- Kilbourne, W., McDonagh, P., & Prothero, A. (1997). Sustainable Consumption and the Quality of Life: A Macromarketing Challenge to the Dominant Social Paradigm. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 24(4), 4-24.
- Koomey, J. G., Berard, S., Sanchez, M., & Wong, H. (2011a). Implications of historical trends in the electrical efficiency of computing. *Annals of the History of Computing, IEEE*, 33(3), 46-54.
- Koomey, J. G., Berard, S., Sanchez, M., & Wong, H. (2011b). Web Extra Appendix: Implications of Historical Trends in the Electrical Efficiency of Computing. *IEEE Annals of the History of Computing*, 33(3), 1-30.

- Kotler, P., & Levy, S. J. (1969). Broadening the concept of marketing. *The Journal of Marketing*, 10-15.
- Kotler, P. (2011). Reinventing Marketing to Manage the Environmental Imperative. *Journal of Marketing*, 75(4), 132-135.
- Liedtke, C., Baedeker, C., Hasselkuss, M., Rohn, H., & Grinewitschus, V. (2015). User-integrated innovation in Sustainable LivingLabs: an experimental infrastructure for researching and developing sustainable product service systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 97, 106-116.
- McCracken, G. D. (1990). *Culture and consumption: New approaches to the symbolic character of consumer goods and activities* (Vol. 1). Indiana University Press.
- McCracken, G. D. (2005). *Culture and consumption II markets, meaning, and brand management*. Indiana University Press.
- McDonagh, P., Dobscha, S., & Prothero, A. (2012). Sustainable Consumption and Production. Challenges for Transformative Consumer Research. In D. G. Mick, S. Pettigrew, C. C. Pechmann, & J. L. Ozanne (Eds.), *Transformative consumer research for personal and collective well-being* (pp. 267-281). Routledge.
- Meyer, C., & Kirby, J. (2010). Leadership in the Age of Transparency. *Harvard business review*, 88(4), 38-46.
- Mickoleit, A. (2010). *Greener and Smarter. ICTs, the Environment and Climate Change*.
- Mitchell, R. W., Wooliscroft, B., & Higham, J. (2010). Sustainable market orientation: A new approach to managing marketing strategy. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 30(2), 160-170.
- Mittelstaedt, J. D., Shultz, C. J., Kilbourne, W. E., & Peterson, M. (2014). Sustainability as Megatrend: Two Schools of Macromarketing Thought. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 34(3), 253-264.
- Mont, O., & Plepys, A. (2008). Sustainable consumption progress: should we be proud or alarmed? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16(4), 531-537.
- Moore, S. B., & Manring, S. L. (2009). Strategy development in small and medium sized enterprises for sustainability and increased value creation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 17(2), 276-282.
- Oakey, R. P. (2003). Technical entrepreneurship in high technology small firms: some observations on the implications for management. *Technovation*, 23(8), 679-688.
- Papaoikonomou, E., & Alarcón, A. (2015). Revisiting Consumer Empowerment: An Exploration of Ethical Consumption Communities. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 1-17.
- Peterson, M. (2013). *Sustainable enterprise. A macromarketing approach*. SAGE.

- Pettersen, I. N. (2016). Fostering absolute reductions in resource use: the potential role and feasibility of practice-oriented design. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 132, 252-265.
- Pieters, R. (2013). Bidirectional dynamics of materialism and loneliness: Not just a vicious cycle. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 40(4), 615-631.
- Pirages, D. C., & Ehrlich, P. R. (1974). *Ark II social response to environmental imperatives*. Freeman.
- Podoshen, J. S., & Andrzejewski, S. A. (2012). An examination of the relationships between materialism, conspicuous consumption, impulse buying, and brand loyalty. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 20(3), 319-334.
- Princen, T. (2005). *The logic of sufficiency*. MIT Press.
- Rouăinia, M. (2014, May 14 – 17). *ICT's solution for a better environment* Digital Proceeding Of The ICOEST'2014, Side, Turkey.
- Saatcioglu, B., & Corus, C. (2019). Towards a macromarketing and consumer culture theory intersection: participatory and deliberative methodologies. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 39(1), 9-24.
- Sandberg, M., & Polska, P. (2015). *Efficiency or Sufficiency? The (Re) Construction of Discourses about Sustainable Consumption in Marketing Research* Annual Macromarketing Conference,
- Sandberg, M. (2021). Sufficiency transitions: A review of consumption changes for environmental sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 293, 126097.
- Schmutzer, M. E. A. (1994). *Ingenium und Individuum: eine sozialwissenschaftliche Theorie von Wissenschaft und Technik*. Springer-Verlag.
- Schäfer, M., Ohlhorst, D., Schön, S., & Kruse, S. (2010). Science for the future: challenges and methods for transdisciplinary sustainability research. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 2(1), 114-137.
- Shapiro, S. J. (2009). Macromarketing. In S. Andersson & G. Svensson (Eds.), *Glocal Marketing: Think Globally and Act Locally*. Studentlitteratur AB.
- Stiel, F., & Teuteberg, F. (2015). *Sustainable Consumption of Information and Communication Technologies in a Digital Society – Dialogue and Transformation through Open Innovation* Global Cleaner Production and Sustainable Consumption Conference Sitges, Barcelona.
- Sunikka-Blank, M., & Galvin, R. (2012). Introducing the rebound effect: the gap between performance and actual energy consumption. *Building Research and Information*, 40(3), 260-273.
- Svenson, F., Mäschtig, F., & Meier, A. (2018). Contrasting brand community support for sustainable smartphone practices of charging and managing battery power. *Proceedings of the MKWI*, 1183-1194.
- Svenson, F. (2018). Smartphone crises and adjustments in a virtual P3 community—doing sustainability oriented smartphone consumption. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 34(7-8), 664-693.

- Svenson, F. (2019): Repair practices in a virtual smartphone community – fostering more sustainable usage through branding, ephemera. theory & politics in organization, 19:2, 325-344. 10.5281/zenodo.18108000
- Tukker, A., Cohen, M. J., Hubacek, K., & Mont, O. (2010). The Impacts of Household Consumption and Options for Change. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 14(1), 13-30.
- Willmott, H. (1997). Management and organization studies as science? *Organization*, 4(3), 309-344.
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development. (2008). Sustainable consumption facts and trends, Geneva.